

Transformation of Sucrose : An Alternative Route for Amination

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Mesylation of sucrose with 1 and 2 moles of mesylchloride (methane sulfonyl chloride) separately followed by acetylation in pyridine formed mono-, di-, tri- and tetra-O-mesyl sucrose-acetates respectively. Mono and dimesyl sucrose-acetates are converted into their amino derivatives via iodo and azido compounds in appreciable yields.

HOCKETT and ZIEF¹ reported the formation of sulfonyl esters of sucrose by reaction with mesyl or tosyl chlorides (*p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride) in pyridine solution at 0°. They recorded the analytical values for the amorphous powders of tri-O-tosyl, octa-O-tosyl and octa-O-mesyl sucrose derivatives. Lemieux and Barrette² carried out tri-O-tosylation of sucrose and on chromatographic analysis of the mixture formed they obtained di-, tri-, tetra- and penta-O-tosyl-sucroses in 1 : 1 : 0.33 : 0.5 molar ratios respectively. Issacs and coworkers³ prepared 1'-6-6' tri-O-tosyl sucrose pentaacetate and confirmed its structure by converting it into 1', 4 : 3, 6 : 3', 6' tri anhydrosucrose by treating it with sodium methoxide in methanol.

Khan⁴ confirmed the findings of Issacs and coworkers by preparing the 1', 4 : 3, 6 : 3', 6' tri anhydrosucrose from 1'-6-6' tri-O-tosyl sucrose and its benzoate derivatives by treating with sodium methoxide in methanol.

A large number of nucleophilic substitution reaction on sulfonyl esters of sucrose have been studied by various workers⁵⁻⁹ from time to time. In the present work the preparation of mono- and di-mesyl sucrose acetates by mesylation of sucrose (1 mole) with mesylchloride (1 and 2 moles separately) in pyridine followed by acetylation with acetic anhydride in the same solution has been carried out to study the reactivities of -OH groups of sucrose. Products obtained on nucleophilic substitution with sodium iodide and sodium azide separately gave the iodo and azido derivatives of sucrose respectively.

Azido derivatives of sucrose have also been prepared in good yield and comparatively at low temperature by replacement of iodo group by azido group. Azido derivatives of sucrose on reduction with platinum oxide gave amino sucroses. This provides an alternative route for the preparation of amino sucroses to that of previous workers from the chlorodeoxy sugars^{7,10-12} which required higher temperature such as 80-90° and in comparatively lower yields.

Experimental

General : All evaporations were carried out under reduced pressure below 50°. Melting points were recorded in capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were measured on a Bellingham-Stanley type I polarimeter in 1 dm tubes. Column chromatography on silica gel was carried out at room temperature using BDH, India (60-120 mesh) silica gel activated at 120° before use. Thin layer chromatography was performed at room temperature on silica gel G (BDH, India). The spraying reagent used was 10% solution of conc. H₂SO₄ in ethanol. NMR spectra were recorded in chloroform-d at Varian XI-100 FT NMR spectrometer with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. All the solvents used were BDH, India dried and freshly distilled before use.

Monomesylsucrose heptaacetate : Mesylchloride (1.14 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of sucrose (5 g) and pyridine (100 ml) at 0° in 15 to 20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr at 0° and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hr. Acetic anhydride (12 ml) was added dropwise in the same reaction mixture at room temperature and the reaction mixture was kept for 24 hr. The reaction product was poured with stirring into iced water, the powdery product was filtered off, dried and dissolved in acetone. Acetone solution was decolorized with activated animal charcoal, filtered and poured with stirring into iced water. White amorphous powder (7.3 g) showed on tlc, chloroform : acetone (5 : 1), a fast moving fraction (sucrose octaacetate) and four slower moving products. Product obtained (6 g) on elution from silica gel (200 g) with chloroform : acetone (7 : 1) gave following.

Mixture of 6- and 6'-mono-O-mesylsucrose heptaacetate (1) : (0.6 g, 5.8%), R_f value 0.56 (chloroform : acetone 5 : 1), m.p. 62-63°, [α]_D²⁰ +49.7° (c 2.1, chloroform) (Found : C, 45.4 ; H, 5.3 ; S, 4.1. C₂₇H₃₈O₂₀S requires C, 45.3 ; H, 5.3 ; S, 4.48%).

NMR data (CDCl₃): τ 4.28, 4.37 (2d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1), 4.94 (t, 1 proton $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4), 5.11 (dd, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2), 6.88 (s, 3 protons, 1 Ms), 7.74-8.14 (m, 21 protons, 7Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping.

6,6'-Di-O-mesylysucrose hexaacetate (2): (1.5 g, 13.6%), R_f value 0.46 (chloroform: acetone 5:1) was then eluted and isolated as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 67-68°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 50.2^\circ$ (c, 1.16, chloroform) (Found: C, 41.3; H, 5.0; S, 8.2. C₂₆H₃₈O₁₁S₂ requires C, 41.6; H, 5.0; S, 8.5%).

NMR data (CDCl₃): τ 4.33 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1), 4.95 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4), 5.11 (dd, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2), 6.8-6.96 (m, 6 protons, 2 Ms), 7.74-8.14 (m, 18 protons, 6 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping.

1',6,6'-Tri-O-mesylysucrose pentaacetate (3): (1.2 g, 10.4%), R_f value 0.36 (chloroform: acetone 5:1) was then eluted and isolated as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 72-73°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 46.8^\circ$ (c, 1.18 chloroform) (Found: C, 37.9; H, 4.8; S, 11.8. C₂₄H₃₄O₁₀S₃ requires C, 38.1; H, 4.83, S, 12.2%).

NMR data (CDCl₃): τ 4.28 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1), 4.91 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4), 5.06 (dd, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2), 6.7-7.0 (m, 9 protons, 3 Ms), 7.62-8.12 (m, 15 protons, 5 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping.

1',2,6,6'-Tetra-O-mesylysucrose tetraacetate (4): (0.6 g, 5%), R_f value 0.26 (chloroform: acetone 5:1) was then eluted and isolated as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 76-77°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 46.9^\circ$ (c 1.05, chloroform) (Found: C, 34.9; H, 4.5; S, 15.1. C₂₄H₃₄O₁₀S₄ requires: C, 35.0; H, 4.6; S, 15.6%).

NMR data (CDCl₃): τ 4.26 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1), 6.7-7.1 (m, 12 protons, 4 Ms), 7.7-8.1 (m, 12 protons, 4 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping.

Dimesylysucrose hexaacetate: Mesityl chloride (2.3 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of sucrose (5 g) and pyridine (100 ml) at 0° in 15 to 20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr at 0° and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hr. Acetic anhydride (25 ml) was added dropwise in the same reaction mixture at room temperature and the reaction mixture was worked up in the same way as in monomesylysucrose heptaacetate. Product obtained (8 g) on elution from silica gel (300 g) with chloroform: acetone (7:1) gave 1 (0.96 g, 9.2%); 2 (2 g, 18%); 3 (2 g, 17.4%) and 4 (1.36 g, 11.3%).

6- and 6'-Monoiodo-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (5): Sodium iodide (0.3 g) was added to a solution of 1 (0.5 g) in butanone (20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 6 hr when the tlc indicated that the yield of monoiodide

was optimal and the reaction was stopped. Sodium methane sulfonate and unreacted sodium iodide were filtered off and washed with ice-cold butanone. The filtrate was concentrated to a syrup which was dissolved in chloroform and washed with sodium thiosulfate solution and water to remove the dissolved free iodine in the solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered and concentrated to a syrup which was chromatographed on silica gel (30 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone (6:1) gave a syrup 5 (0.31 g, 60%) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 40.2^\circ$ (c 1.12, chloroform) (Found: C, 41.4; H, 4.6; I, 16.5. C₂₆H₃₈O₁₁I requires C, 41.8; H, 4.7; I, 17.02%).

6,6'-Diiodo-6,6'-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (6a). *6- and 6'-monoiodo-monodeoxy-monomesylysucrose hexaacetate*, 6b: A sample (1 g) of 2 was iodinated with sodium iodide (0.7 g) as described in the synthesis of 5, yielded a syrup which was chromatographed on silica gel (40 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone (7:1) gave initially 6a (0.45 g, 40%) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 26.6^\circ$ (c 0.97, chloroform) (Found: C, 35.0; H, 3.8; I, 29.6. C₂₄H₃₂O₁₀I₂ requires C, 35.4; H, 3.9; I, 31.2%) and 6 (0.26 g, 25%) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 33.6^\circ$ (c 0.7, chloroform) (Found: C, 37.9; H, 4.2; I, 15.7. C₂₆H₃₈O₁₁SI requires C, 38.3; H, 4.5; I, 16.2%).

NMR data (CDCl₃): τ 4.23, 4.36 (2d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1), 4.92 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4), 5.1 (dd, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2), 6.5 (d, H-6 and 6') 6.85 (s, 3 protons, 1 Ms), 7.74-8.0 (m, 19 protons, 6 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping.

6- and 6'-Monoazido-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (7): A mixture 1 (0.5 g) and sodium azide (0.25 g) in N,N-dimethylformamide (15 ml) was heated at 85° for 30 hr under agitation. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated. The residue was acetylated with acetic anhydride in pyridine to acetylate the deacetylated groups in usual manner to a product which was chromatographed on silica gel (40 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone (7:1) gave a glassy solid 7 (0.34 g, 74% $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 56.0^\circ$ (c 0.9, chloroform) (Found: C, 47.1; H, 5.1; N, 6.2. C₂₆H₃₈O₁₁N₃ requires C, 47.2; H, 5.3; N, 6.35%).

6,6'-Diazido-6,6'-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (8): A mixture of 2 (0.5 g) and sodium azide (0.3 g) in N,N-dimethylformamide (15 ml) was heated at 110° for 30 hr under agitation. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The residue was acetylated with acetic anhydride in pyridine as usual to a product which was chromatographed on silica gel (40 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone (7:1) gave a syrupy product 8, (0.34 g, 82%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 5.5^\circ$ (c, 2.1, chloroform) (Found: C, 44.3; H, 4.7; N, 12.9. C₂₄H₃₂O₁₀N₆ requires 44.7; H, 4.9, N, 13.0%).

6- and 6'-Monoazido-monodeoxysucrose (9): A solution of 7 (0.4 g) in dry methanol (30 ml) was treated with 2 M methanolic sodium methoxide

(1 ml) at room temperature for 5 hr with stirring, tlc (chloroform : ethanol, 5:3) then showed one product running slower than the starting material. After neutralisation with Amberlite IR 120 (H⁺) resin (freshly regenerated and washed with methanol before use), the solution was concentrated to a syrup. The syrupy residue was boiled with light petroleum which was then decanted carefully. This operation was repeated three to four times to remove all of the methyl acetate. The product was dried over phosphoric oxide and paraffin wax overnight to give the monoazide as a syrup **9** (0.2 g, 91% [α]_D²⁰ +58.4° (c 1.5, water) (Found : C, 38.8 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 11.1. C₁₂H₂₂O₁₀N₃ requires C, 39.2 ; H, 5.7 ; N, 11.4%).

6,6'-Diazido-6,6'-dideoxysucrose (10) : A sample of **8** (0.3 g) was deacetylated with 2M methanolic sodium methoxide (1 ml) as described in the synthesis of **9** gave the diazide as a syrup **10**, (0.14 g, 81%) [α]_D²⁰ +61° (c 1.4, water) (Found : C, 36.2 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 21.1. C₁₂H₂₀O₈N₆ requires C, 36.7 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 21.4%).

6- and 6'-Monoamine-monodeoxysucrose (11) : **9** (0.15 g) was hydrogenated in 50% aqueous ethanol (50 ml) in the presence of Adam's platinum oxide (50 mg) at 3.4 Kg/cm² of hydrogen atmosphere at 35-40° for 20 hr. After the catalyst was removed, the solution was concentrated and crystallized from ethanol : methanol : water (3 : 3 : 4 v/v) in refrigerator for 20 days to give **11**, (90 mg, 70%), m. p. 137-138° (dec.) [α]_D²⁰ +60.5° (c 0.8, water) (Found : C, 42.0 ; H, 6.4 ; N, 4.0. C₁₂H₂₅O₁₀N requires C, 42.2 ; H, 6.8 ; N, 4.1%).

6,6'-Diamino-6,6'-dideoxysucrose (12) : **10** (0.1 g) was hydrogenated with Adam's platinum oxide as described in the synthesis of **11**. After the catalyst was removed, the solution was concentrated and crystallized from ethanol : methanol : water (2 : 2 : 4 v/v) in a refrigerator for 20 days to give **12**, (64 mg, 80%), m. p. 126-129° (dec) [α]_D²⁰ +63° (c 0.54, methanol) (Found : C, 42.1 ; H, 7.0 ; N, 8.1. C₁₂H₂₄O₈N₂ requires C, 42.3 ; H, 7.0 ; N, 8.2%).

6- and 6'-Monoazido-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (7) from 5 : A mixture of **5** (0.5) and sodium azide (0.25 g) in N, N-dimethylformamide (15 ml) was stirred for 48 hr under agitation at 25°. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate on dispersing into iced water gave a white amorphous powder which was decolorized with activated animal charcoal, filtered and filtrate concentrated to a syrup which was chromatographed on silica gel (30 g) with carbon tetrachloride : acetone (7 : 1) gave a glassy solid **7**, (0.41 g, 95%), [α]_D²⁰ +56.5° (c, 0.8, chloroform) (Found : C, 47.0 ; N, 6.1 ; H, 4.9. C₂₄H₃₅O₁₇N₃ requires C, 47.2 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 6.35%).

6,6'-Diazido-6,6'-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (8) from 6a : A mixture of **6a** (0.4 g) and sodium azide (0.3 g) in N, N-dimethylformamide (15 ml) was stirred at 35° for 50 hr under agitation. The reaction mixture was worked up as described in the

synthesis of **7** from **5** and on purification by chromatography on silica gel (30 g) carbon tetrachloride : acetone (7 : 1) gave a syrupy product **8**, (0.29 g, 94%), [α]_D²⁰ +5.5° (c 2.0, chloroform) (Found : C, 44.1 ; H, 4.5 ; N, 12.7. C₂₄H₃₂O₁₅N₆ requires C, 44.7 ; H, 4.9 ; N, 13.0%).

Results and Discussion

Mesylation of sucrose (1 mole) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1 and 2 moles) in pyridine at 0° and acetylation by acetic anhydride in the same solution at room temperature gave the product which on chromatographic separation and purification gave mono-O-mesyl sucrose heptaacetate (1), di-O-mesylysucrose hexaacetate (2), tri-O-mesylysucrose pentaacetate (3) and tetra-O-mesyl sucrose tetraacetate (4). The first product 1 was a (2 : 1) mixture of 6 and 6'-mono-O-mesylysucrose heptaacetate as revealed by nmr spectrum which showed the doublets in low field (τ 4.28, 4.36) due to H-1 in the 6 and 6' mono-O-mesylysucrose heptaacetates. This showed that the reactivities of 6- and 6'-hydroxyl groups in sucrose are 0-6 $\geq$ 0-6'. Products **2**, **3** and **4** were 6-6'-di-O-mesyl, 1'-6-6'-tri-O-mesyl and 1',2,6,6'-tetra-O-mesylysucrose acetates respectively as confirmed by their nmr spectra. In comparison with the ¹H nmr data for octa-O-acetylsucrose, the signals due to the protons attached to the carbon having sulfonyl groups appeared at a slightly higher fields.

The formation of products **1,2,3,4**, clearly showed that decreasing order of reactivity of different -OH groups in sucrose is as follows :

Fig. 1

- | | |
|------------------------------|---|
| (1). R=OMs ; R'=R''=R'''=OAc | (6b). R=I, R'=OMs ; R''=R'''=OAc |
| (2). R=R'=OMs ; R''=R'''=OAc | (7). R=N ₃ ; R'=R''=R'''=OAc |
| (3). R=R'=R''=OMs ; R'''=OAc | R'=N ₃ |
| (4). R=R'=R''=R'''=OMs | R=R'=R''=OAc |
| (5). R=I, R'=R''=R'''=OAc | (8). R=R'=N ₃ ; R''=R'''=OAc |
| (6a). R=R'=I, R''=R'''=OAc | |

Fig. 2

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| (9). R=N ₃ ; R'=OH | (11). R=NH ₂ ; R'=OH |
| R'=N ₃ ; R=OH | R'=NH ₂ ; R=OH |
| (10). R=R'=N ₃ | (12). R=R'=NH ₂ |

Investigation of the reaction of **1** with sodium iodide in butanone gave the mixture of 6- and 6'-mono-iodo-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (**5**). Similarly reaction of **2** with sodium iodide in butanone gave 6,6'-diiodo-6,6'-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (**6a**) and 6- and 6'-monoiodo-monodeoxy-monomesylsucrose hexaacetate (**6b**).

6b was a (3 : 1) mixture of 6- and 6'-monoiodo-monodeoxy-monomesylsucrose hexaacetate as revealed by nmr which showed two doublets in low field (τ 4.23, 4.36) and one doublet (τ 6.53) of 2 protons H-6 and H-6' (due to overlapping of two doublets of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{I}$ because of the mixture of 6- and 6'-monoiodo-monodeoxy-monomesylsucrose hexaacetate). **1** and **2** with sodium azide in N,N-dimethylformamide gave the mixture of 6- and 6'-monoazido-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (**7**) and 6,6'-diazido-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (**8**).

7 and **8** on deacetylation with 2 M methanolic sodium methoxide in absolute methanol gave the mixture of 6- and 6'-monoazido-monodeoxysucrose (**9**) and 6,6'-diazide-6,6'-dideoxysucrose (**10**).

9 and **10** on catalytic hydrogenation with platinum oxide (Adam's catalyst) under pressure 3.4 kg/cm² of hydrogen atmosphere at 35-40° for 20 hr gave the mixture of 6- and 6'-monoamino-monodeoxysucrose (**11**) and 6,6'-diamino-6,6'-dideoxysucrose (**12**).

Replacement of iodo-substituents in the 6- and 6'-monoiodo-monodeoxysucrose heptaacetate (**5**) and 6,6'-diiodo-6,6'-dideoxysucrose hexaacetate (**6a**) by azide was readily achieved in N,N-dimethylformamide to **7** and **8** in 95 and 84% yields respectively.

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